

Addressing Energy Efficiency and Sustainability Challenges in the EU's Built Environment: A Data-Driven Approach

Spyridon Kousouris¹, Anastasios Tsitsanis¹, Sotiris Kousouris¹

¹ Suite5 Data Intelligence Solutions Limited, Cyprus

E-mail: spiros@suite5.eu, tasos@suite5.eu, sotiris@suite5.eu

Abstract

The EU is increasingly acknowledging the urgent need to tackle energy efficiency and sustainability challenges in the built environment. With buildings accounting for 40% of the EU's energy consumption and 36% of energy-related greenhouse gas emissions, new regulations have emerged to meet the targets set by the European Green Deal and the new European Bauhaus. To tackle these issues effectively, there is a growing need for advanced technologies that enable the optimisation of buildings' operations and energy performance, by utilising insights deriving from building-energy data and AI-enabled analytics. Recognising this need, our methodology provides a comprehensive solution for data-driven buildings' energy performance optimisation through the introduction of innovative energy services bundles contributing to a more sustainable and energy-efficient built environment. The approach focuses on three core aspects: (i) developing a cloud-based platform enabling seamless and interoperable collection and processing of data towards effectively powering various innovative energy (and non-energy) services for the whole building sector value chain (building managers, energy retailers, etc.), (ii) leverage advanced AI analytics to ingest the required intelligence and insights in building energy performance optimisation applications/services, enabling the participation of buildings in energy markets in the frame of Demand Response programmes, (iii) create a data sharing-driven energy services ecosystem, through a secure, privacy preserving data trading/sharing marketplace; enabling data exchanges among stakeholders, fostering collaboration and innovation in building-energy services.

Keywords (5 words): Building Energy Optimisation, Building-Energy Data Marketplace, Data sharing-driven energy services, Data Consumer

1 Introduction

Presently, there has been a growing recognition within the European Union (EU) of the pressing need to confront energy efficiency and sustainability issues in the built environment. Buildings which currently almost dominate the European energy sector, accounting for a substantial 40% of the EU's energy consumption and a significant 36% of its energy-related greenhouse gas emissions [1], have come under the spotlight due to their significant environmental impact. In this direction, the EU has taken bold steps forward in its commitment to environmental sustainability; most notably through the European Green Deal and the New European Bauhaus initiative. These initiatives set forth ambitious goals that require innovative solutions. To effectively meet these objectives, there is a clear understanding of the importance of advanced technologies capable of optimising building operations and energy performance. These optimisation efforts, guided by data-driven insights and supported by Artificial Intelligence (AI)-enabled analytics, are seen as pivotal to achieving the EU's vision of a more sustainable future.

In this context, this paper presents a comprehensive methodology designed to address the pressing challenges of buildings' energy efficiency and sustainability within the EU's built environment; by introducing an integrated cloud-based platform; namely the BEYOND Big data platform, developed within the EU-funded project BEYOND-H2020 [2]. End-users of the platform (such as data providers/owners, data consumers and data brokers) are provided with a set of innovative services bundles to enhance sustainability and energy efficiency in the building sector. Simultaneously, it fosters a secure data exchange ecosystem enabling monetisation of buildings' data through the delivery of a data marketplace, where users can exchange/trade their data assets. In addition, the

BEYOND Big data platform offers advance AI analytic services, where users can extract meaningful insights from the data they own or have legitimate acquired through the platform's Marketplace. In Chapter 2, the background and motivation of the proposed solution is described, acting as the basis to extract the principles that underlie the design of the different technical novelties offered by the BEYOND Big data platform and which are presented in Chapter 3. Following, Chapter 4 outlines the interactions of the platform with several other big data-powered applications/ tools (also developed in the context of the project), highlighting the added value brought by BEYOND to the every-day data exchanges that take place among stakeholders.

2 Background-Motivation

2.1 EU's Holistic Approach to Building Energy Efficiency.

Acknowledging that the building sector can play a crucial role in effective climate policy, the efficient use of building's energy and its conservation/optimization is on top of EU's agenda [3]. Several European regulations and strategies have emerged and are regularly revised, urging EU member states to set stricter regulations regarding the efficient use of energy in buildings, including: the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (2010/31/EU)[4] aspiring to achieve a carbon-neutral building sector by 2050, through the promotion of advanced technologies. Its more recent version, the Revised Energy Performance of Buildings Directive [5] mandates a decrease in buildings' energy usage and promotes the definition of smart building; by introducing the smart readiness indicator (SRI), as a metric capable of evaluating a building's technological ability/preparedness to adapt to the needs of its occupants and to enhance its energy efficiency and overall performance. This directive also aims to provide more comprehensive and accurate data about buildings to market participants by gathering real-time energy consumption figures and enhancing the Energy Performance Certificates (EPC) databases making them more reliable, user-friendly, and comparable across member states.

Moreover, the Revised Energy Efficiency Directive (2023) raises the EU's energy efficiency target, making it binding for EU countries to collectively ensure an additional 11.7% reduction in energy consumption by 2030, compared to the 2020 reference scenario projections [6] Moreover, further regulations were established towards EU-wide consistent rules for improving the environmental and energy performance of buildings and their related products (e.g., building devices). These include the Eco-Design directive (2009/125/EC) [7] while not building specific, it establishes a framework for setting eco-design requirements for energy-related products sold in the EU; covering a wide range of products, including those relevant to building energy efficiency like heating equipment, water heaters, and more. Similarly, the Energy Labelling protocol (2010/30/EU) [8] complementing the Eco-design Directive sets labelling requirements that provide consumers with information about the energy efficiency and other essential performance metrics of products.

All these efforts align with the broader ambition to achieve a carbon-neutral Europe by 2050, a key objective of the European Green Deal, which essentially provides a roadmap to transform the EU into a resource-efficient and competitive economy where there are no net emissions of greenhouse gases by 2050 [9]. Among its various initiatives, the Green Deal emphasises the renovation of existing buildings to improve their energy efficiency. Through its Renovation Wave Strategy (launched in 2020), the EU recognised the multi-fold benefits of building renovation (such as reducing energy bills, decreasing greenhouse gas emissions, and stimulating the construction industry), focusing particularly on public buildings and social housing, aiming for 35 million buildings to be renovated by 2030 [10].

The EU has adopted a multi-faceted approach, that combines regulatory frameworks with financial incentives, such as the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and the Cohesion Fund, to support energy efficiency projects in its member states. Such an approach underscores its commitment to transform the building sector into a more energy-efficient and environmentally sustainable one. Taking into consideration that the 2050 horizon for a carbon-neutral Europe "approaches", it's evident that buildings will play a pivotal role in the broader climate strategy and

the need for embracing technological advancements is imperative; not only to serve the purpose of energy efficiency but also to elevate the overall quality of life for building occupants.

2.2 Buildings' AI-driven Energy efficiency: Opportunities & Challenges

Given the rapid progress in technology and its broader accessibility, buildings are evolving into intelligent ones commonly referred to as smart buildings. This evolution is strongly supported by the generation of vast amounts of data, stemming from various sources including IoT devices, (offering data related to devices' management and users' operations), Building Energy Management Systems (BEMS), smart meters, renewable energy generation, etc. This data is characterised by its ever-expanding nature, varying degrees of spatio-temporal detail, and their enormous volumes. Notably, having access to such expansive data pools offers significant potentials for refining the monitoring and optimisation of buildings, which in turn can result in improved energy efficiency. This can be accomplished by a thorough comprehension and in-depth analysis of all aspects that either directly or indirectly affect their operation and energy consumption and can be facilitated through the use of advanced Big Energy Data Analytics techniques [11]. These techniques incorporate technologies and tools of Big Data management and AI analytics; with the latter offering the capability to process vast amount of data at unprecedented speeds and can recognise patterns that might be missed by human analysts, provide actionable insights, and reveal trends.

Studies have shown that in buildings where data are generated in vast amounts, the incorporation of AI-based approaches can deliver significant opportunities for energy efficiency, renewable energy forecasting and energy accessibility; while enabling also active customer participation (e.g., in demand response programs) typically using machine learning (ML) algorithms and leveraging blockchain to protect data [12]. This is also supported within studies identifying that utilisation of big data and AI, can optimise demand response and end-use energy efficiency, as well as reduce energy bills on the respective premises. Even at a broader scope, studies showed also that the advantages of AI in smart buildings can extend and influence urban areas, fostering environmental preservation, reducing building maintenance costs, and promoting buildings' energy conservation [13],[14],[15].

Yet, even with an understanding of Big Data analytics' potential, the building-energy sector (a data intensive sector) has not greatly capitalised on its bulk generated data, because of slow technology adoption [11]. Big Data analytics has beneficially influenced every industry that has incorporated it into their product or services delivered; being fundamental when there is a need of managing and analysing vast amounts of data [16]. Industries like telecommunications, healthcare, and finance, heavily dependent on digital data for their operation, extensively use big data [17]; however, less technology-driven industries such as construction and manufacturing, are lagging behind. Studies investigating the various barriers hindering a wide adoption of big data technologies in the building/construction sector identified main issues being: the high investment cost, the lack of government support and regulations, lack of technology expertise, inadequate data capture knowledge, etc., [18]. In addition, key technological barriers include limited access to technology [19], absence of appropriate data platforms capable of managing such enormous diverse datasets and interoperability challenges [20]. While data-related barriers focus on security concerns and difficulties in accessing sensitive/private data (i.e., lack of access control policies) [21], unsuitable data description/labelling (i.e., lack of proper metadata), improper data quality, capturing of irrelevant data, etc., [22].

A promising strategy to address these challenges, is to take away the data management and analytics processes from the stakeholders, thereby simplify the process, which may reshape their perspectives. In its place, stakeholders can be presented with clear insights (through comprehensive dashboards) sourced from sophisticated data analysis, using pretrained algorithms for diverse contexts and business situations. Adopting such a strategy can signify the beginning of unlocking data-driven optimisation methods, that potentially can result in a favourable return on investment (ROI). Consequently, this will also pave the way to efficiently tackle operational and business barriers underlining the importance of the extensive data generated in the context of buildings.

Comparable methods and successful applications are evident in relevant case studies, especially in the United States. There, incorporation of sophisticated, near-real-time data analytics within the building sector has been pivotal for detecting irregularities early on, pinpointing trends, identifying possible security issues, and addressing other issues that might lead to considerable economic setbacks. Moreover, this has paved the way for decreasing expenses and unveiling new opportunities for revenue generation [24].

Notably, the benefits of advanced big data analysis benefit both consumers, but also cater to the needs of building and facility managers by significantly cutting down on energy costs and fine-tuning energy efficiency. Building's predictive maintenance functions can also be enhanced, (relevant for facility managers), since through such analysis faults can be identified, enabling proactive maintenance, and issuing relevant alerts and notifications. Moreover, it paves the way for new earning avenues by engaging in adaptable dealings within energy trading platforms. In our contemporary cities, data-driven energy solutions are crucial in finding the right equilibrium between energy conservation and ensuring urban residents' comfort and health. These solutions, anchored in people-focused automation and fortified with enhanced safety measures beyond just energy, present real value for those in pursuit of ideal living environments.

2.3 The Value of Sharing Building's data

Buildings' data, whether it be energy consumption patterns, occupancy rates, or HVAC operation metrics hold significant value. When this data is shared appropriately, can drive innovation, enable informed decision-making, and optimise the built environment to unprecedented levels. The opportunities that arise from sharing building data among the various stakeholders of the building-energy value chain being directly or indirectly tied to buildings' energy performance, (e.g., Energy Network Operators, Public Authorities, ESCOs, AEC Industry, District Heating Network Operators, etc.), are immense. For example, energy network operators, with access to real-time building consumption data, can forecast demand more accurately; leading to better grid management by analysing data derived from buildings and fine-tune operational schedules. All of this can be achieved through the integration of cutting-edge technologies like AI, Machine Learning (ML), and Big Data; which improves the effectiveness of Network Operational Planning tools that seamlessly fuse simulation models with AI algorithms to benefit for real-time data-driven insights. In a similar fashion, ESCOs can customise their energy solutions; by targeting specific inefficiencies revealed by the shared data, and devising strategies for energy conservation, tailoring solutions to specific building types and user behaviours. For Energy Retailers, the adoption of advanced data analytics paves the way for their transition from mere energy suppliers to pioneering energy service facilitators, adopting the Energy-as-a-Service paradigm. This shift will not only amplify their profit margins but also position them to deliver tailor-made energy solutions to their clients. Moreover, it facilitates portfolio enhancement via strategic billing and specialised campaigns, aligning with EU-directed energy efficiency standards. Similarly, Aggregators utilising data analytics can delve deeper into the flexibility capacities within diverse segments of their building portfolio. Such insights can enable them to precisely create Virtual Power Plants (VPPs), catering to the fluctuating demands of electric grid managers for balancing and ancillary services. Moreover, Local Authorities can gain insights to enact effective regulations, planning for urban growth, while ensuring that environmental and energy efficiency standards are maintained. The construction industry, on the other hand, can leverage this data in design processes to construct buildings that are both functional and efficient by design. Thus, minimising interventions during the actual operation of buildings to ensure the economic viability of Energy Performance Contracts.

However, sharing building data comes with several challenges. Data privacy and security concerns are on top of the list. Thus, it is imperative to ensure that shared data does not violate the privacy rights of individuals or compromise building security. Also, data harmonisation/standardisation is another significant challenge. As the building industry encompasses a wide range of different sectors, ensuring that data formats, units, and metrics are uniform and standardised becomes critical for accomplishing interoperability. Another challenge is that of data accuracy; since erroneous data can

lead to wrong results and ultimately in misguided strategies and with such diverse data sources, ensuring accuracy becomes paramount.

It is evident from the above, that a building data sharing ecosystem is a symbiotic one; where each stakeholder brings to the table a unique perspective towards harnessing collective knowledge and intelligence, that can transform future buildings to more energy efficient and sustainable. Therefore, the key lies in addressing the challenges head-on, creating an environment of trust, and fostering collaborations that put these vast volumes of data to the best possible use.

3 Methodology

In response to the aforementioned challenges and requirements, the BEYOND project introduces a reference big data management platform, namely the BEYOND Big data platform. It incorporates advanced data collection and harmonisation services, data sharing/trading services, complemented by advanced AI analytics capabilities; the latter enabling the provision of insights and derived data from a combination of actual (near real-time) building information and data from diverse external sources.

The platform's data collection services enable users to ingest data from various sources related directly or indirectly to the building sector, such as historical data, APIs, statistical data, sensor and IoT data, weather information, open data sources, etc. Through advanced AI analytics services, users can utilise their data to enhance intelligence and get valuable insights on the actual energy performance of their building(s). This can be achieved through the design of analytics solutions (pipelines) or use of pretrained algorithms tailored for the building sector and focusing on energy performance understanding and further optimization. Simultaneously, stakeholders involved in the buildings data value chain (who ultimately rely on data streams generated by the building sector), can effectively address their business and optimisation needs. Through the platform's secure data Marketplace, they can enhance their knowledge and intelligence; as it enables them to expand their data accessibility by acquiring or trading a multitude of diverse building energy-related data assets. The integrated BEYOND Big data platform is developed following agile software development methodologies and its beta version has been in operation since April 2022.

Figure 1 BEYOND platform's technical novelties

The design of the BEYOND Big data platform and its offered services is based on real-life business and end-user requirements from different stakeholders of the building data value chain, extracted during the early activities of the BEYOND project. The platform is developed with a strong focus on interoperability, aspiring to bring together various stakeholders. Its aim is to cultivate a data sharing mentality and facilitate interoperable data exchanges. This will support the creation of innovative applications that effectively address building energy performance optimization needs, along with further business objectives of all actors affected by buildings' operation. It promotes centralised data

exchange based on standards-based and interoperable data formats through extensible semantic modeling, mapping, and linking capabilities; while also providing flexible querying and reasoning functions to support these endeavours. Figure 1 above summarises the different technical novelties introduced in the BEYOND Big data platform to support the data-driven optimization of the building sector, as well as the energy system as a whole.

Semantic interoperability within the platform is supported through the development of the BEYOND Common Information model (CIM), harmonising open and standardised models widely adopted in relevant domains (including SAREF4BLDG [29], SAREF4ENER [30], SAREF [31], IFC [32], obXML [33], etc.), also supporting versioning and continuous evolution.

Data Security and privacy is also comprehensively managed in the BEYOND Big data platform using a multifaceted approach. User authentication and authorisation is facilitated by integrating with advanced identity management and access control mechanisms. Data ownership and intellectual property rights protection is accomplished through enforcement of controlled access over data shared by the involved stakeholders acting as data owners/ providers. Thus, data owners are enabled to define the licensing metadata to their data assets, based on predefined Creative Commons [34], Community Data License Agreement [35] and Open Data Commons [36] licenses for public data, or customise the licenses based on their preferences. In addition, to guarantee secure access to the data assets residing in the platform, token-based API authentication is mandatory for all data collection or data retrieval API requests.

In this direction and following an agile approach, the BEYOND Big data platform is built on state-of-the-art technologies and comprises of six core and interconnected services bundles:

- (i) the **Cloud Platform Operations Manager**, tasked with overseeing and orchestrating all platform's operations and resources, security aspects (i.e., authentication and authorisation) and the platform's notification mechanism. It is also responsible for the provision of data usage analytics to data providers (in accordance with GDPR) and the delivery of the open APIs offered by the platform.
- (ii) the **Data Ingestion Services**, facilitating multimodal data uploads (such as simple/batch file upload, uploads through APIs, streaming data subscription) along with pre-processing (data cleaning), semantic mapping and linking of the ingested data into an appropriate form for further usage and analysis in the platform. Moreover, this service bundle enables manipulation of the data to safeguard their privacy, through encryption and anonymisation techniques.
- (iii) The **Polyglot Data Storage Layer**, acting as the platform's core storage layer. This scalable storage layer is responsible for securely and consistently storing both temporary and permanent data, including datasets, ML/DL models, analytics results, reports, etc., along with their metadata; the BEYOND CIM and other security information (e.g., access control policies) essential for the various platform's functions.
- (iv) The **Isolated Data Analytics Containers**, offering a comprehensive AI analytics framework for designing data analytics processes, i.e., analytic pipelines based on structured data. User can utilise a range of ML algorithms (e.g., regression, classification, clustering, forecasting, etc.) and execute them towards exporting valuable insights and/or visualising the resulting outcomes through an intuitive dashboard. In its final version the BEYOND Big data platform incorporates twenty-two pretrained analytics solutions, i.e., pre-trained algorithms which essentially represent the data analytics catalogue of the platform. The catalogue covers a broad range of descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics, and the objective is to reduce the configuration and execution time of the analytics algorithms; since users can just feed their data and easily identify patterns or extract different concept features through the utilisation of transfer learning techniques. These algorithms are focused on *Personal analytics*, which delve into consumer energy habits, comfort choices, and flexibility profiles. Additionally, *Industrial analytics* are covered, emphasising on Building Energy Performance, identifying anomalies, and pinpointing energy inefficiencies, while also taking into account individual flexibility analytics. As part of the pretrained analytics offerings, *Predictive Maintenance analytics*, are also provided, which include fault recognition and alert systems, as well as *Forecasting and Building Flexibility analytics*. Additionally, *baseline Edge analytics* are included, contributing to increasing the building's intelligence; through highly localised functions that step on federated learning techniques and pave the way for automated adjustments and optimisation performed at the edge (e.g., smart home/Building automation). Utilising this diverse mix of

pretrained analytics algorithms, building managers and occupants/consumers, and subsequently external actors involved in the value chain, will be able to leverage the benefits of advance AI Big Data Analytics. Essentially, these AI solutions integrate and utilise data flows from diverse building systems and external inputs (e.g., weather information, pertinent building databases, open-building data, etc.) to produce new insights and hidden knowledge.

v) The **Data Trading Module**, which lies at the core of the platform and offers a secure and trusted data sharing/trading ecosystem, namely the BEYOND Data Marketplace. Via the BEYOND Marketplace, users (data providers and data consumers/brokers) can trade their data assets residing in the platform. This is facilitated through legally binding smart contracts (see Figure 2) based on the involved parties' defined terms, and according to the selected remuneration approach. This approach ensures that all data providers' intellectual property rights (IPR) are protected along the data-contracts' lifecycle. Smart data contracts are stored in the BEYOND Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) infrastructure which safeguards data immutability and non-repudiation of the involved transactions. Moreover, through this bundle, data providers can define the access policies and licences (public, private or confidential) of their data assets (being datasets or algorithmic models), thus ensuring effective access control over the shared assets and safeguarding their personal/ business interests against misuse.

Figure 2 Example of a smart data contract executed for data trading through the BEYOND Marketplace

Lastly, (vi) the **Data Exploration Module**, offers data browsing and exploration features. This enables data consumers to easily discover data assets residing in the platform and which can be of their interest; while allowing them to proceed with requesting access to the relevant datasets, by the respective data providers. Data exploration is based on query intent modelling techniques, supporting the data consumers in iteratively defining their data needs and exploring the results to identify data assets that could potentially improve their business operations. Data Matchmaking capabilities are also incorporated; where users are provided with recommendations of data assets that can be of interest to them, based on their predefined search filters. This overall approach brings a demand-driven mentality to the BEYOND Big data platform, as opposed to the typical supply-driven operation of the data marketplaces.

4 The BEYOND Data-driven Energy-as-a-Service (EaaS) Ecosystem

Optimising the energy performance of buildings and enhancing the operations of all related stakeholders (whether directly or indirectly related to buildings performance) undoubtedly depends on a profound understanding of the challenges faced during the actual building operation. Additionally, it rests on seamless end-to-end interoperable communication and data exchanges among all participants and interconnected systems. These two factors encompass four interrelated domains: physical infrastructures (like buildings, their devices, and their usage, as well as districts and energy networks), human systems (involving occupants and their behavioral patterns), energy markets (including energy pricing, flexibility limits, and the inclusion of small consumers); and broader contextual factors such as weather variations, energy cost fluctuations, and their repercussions on the other domains.

The current technical solutions, business methods, market configurations, and regulatory systems fall short in effectively managing the complexities inherent in the optimisation of smart buildings, and more broadly of smart cities and smart grids. This complexity, especially regarding stakeholder interactions and data-sharing needs, hinders the seamless integration of these interconnected domains. Overall, these shortfalls explain the slow uptake of advanced intelligence within the building industry and the limited uptake of innovative energy services. However, if efficiently utilised these services can bring immense benefits; not just for building managers and residents, but for the entire energy ecosystem linked to buildings; deriving value from both from the data they generate, and the insights gained from analysing building-generated data assets.

Toward realising such benefits, the BEYOND project delivers an innovative and scalable reference platform, on top of which several big data-powered applications and tools are developed, for buildings, city authorities, and energy market stakeholders.

Collectively, these elements form the BEYOND Data-driven Energy-as-a-Service (EaaS) Ecosystem. This ecosystem, aspires to cultivate a collaborative mentality across the value chain, allowing all involved stakeholders to benefit from the sharing of data and intelligence; and collectively tackle common energy system challenges, while satisfying individual business goals. Along these lines, BEYOND aims to drive the Digital Energy Transition across the building and energy sectors and facilitate the achievement of notable advantages by:

- Offering stakeholders in the energy sector (e.g., Network Operators, Retailers, ESCOs, Building/Construction companies, and Public/ City Authorities) the opportunity to access and utilise building information and advanced building data insights; towards improving their own business operations. In fact, relying on building data that are currently beyond their reach can help them enhance their operational procedures, reach their immediate to long-term environmental goals, and boost their financial gains, all based on AI-driven analysis of actual data generated from buildings.
- Achieving significant benefits for buildings, both through enhanced energy efficiency and consequently lowered energy costs; and monetary rewards stemming from buildings' data commercialisation (via data exchange agreements and smart data contracts) or by leveraging building flexibility in upstream energy and flexibility markets.

To achieve on this, the BEYOND Big Data platform is accompanied by a set of innovative energy applications and tools. These tools address not only building's energy performance needs, but also the various business and optimisation requirements of the energy stakeholders. These are stakeholders who participate in the energy system value chain and who rely on various data streams generated by the building sector, so that they can demonstrate and validate the value created for each different stakeholder through processing, analysing, enhancing intelligence, and sharing of diverse data assets with the use of the BEYOND offerings.

Each of these innovative applications/tools aim to enhance optimisation within buildings, while also fostering partnerships that can pave the way for emerging business strategies through the delivery of data-driven and intelligence-enabled energy solutions emphasising on:

- Improved buildings' energy performance and predictive maintenance, facilitating energy savings while increasing self-consumption towards cutting down energy costs of consumers and facility/ building managers.

- Tailored Infrastructure Planning, through refining the planning and size of electricity and district heating network; utilising forecasts of energy demand upsurges, drawn on batch static data from open building databases, which are then fine-tuned using genuine data from actual buildings and their energy systems.
- Enhanced urban monitoring and energy policy planning, via partnerships and data exchanges among public/city authorities and building managers/ facility managers. This helps fulfil vital goals towards transitioning to Smart and Sustainable Cities and Energy Systems, by integrating batch static data from trusted building databases and actual data from individual buildings, along with forecasting artefacts delivered from the BEYOND AI Analytics Toolkit.
- Strategic portfolio analytics for energy retailers, by equipping energy providers with sophisticated analytics to refine their billing practices, avoiding significant imbalance charges, and remain in line with the EU's Energy Efficiency obligations.
- Innovative Flexibility solutions, through the introduction of a distinct application for flexibility segmentation, classification and clustering for aggregators, which can help in shaping efficient Virtual Power Plants and deploying consumer-driven demand response strategies towards the delivery of added value balancing and ancillary services to DSOs, through data sharing between buildings, Aggregators and DSOs.
- Personalised Energy Insights, which enable the delivery of custom energy insights and user-focused intelligent building management solutions from energy providers to their users (i.e., households-energy consumers); complemented by non-energy benefits like increased comfort, air quality preservation and in-home security, realised through mutual data exchanges between Energy Retailers, ESCOs and Building Managers/ Occupants.
- Enhancing the adoption rate of Energy Performance Contracting by using an advanced renovation support tool, which aims for optimised and accurate energy-efficient design of buildings; thus, reducing the gap between the predicted and actual energy performance of buildings and meeting the key business viability requirements of ESCOs for de-risking Energy Performance Contracts.
- Launching innovative services that monitor and certify building energy performance and smart readiness based on actual building data; thus, paving the way for the effective introduction of buildings in energy and flexibility markets in an equal manner to mainstreams balancing and ancillary assets and creating significant opportunities for new revenue generation for the building sector in an evident manner.

5 Conclusions & Next steps

This paper delves into the inspiration and consequently to the specifics of the design and implementation of the integrated BEYOND Big data platform and its' innovative services bundles, pertaining to data collection & harmonisation, data sharing, data trading and AI analytics functions. The platform is based on real-life business and end-users' requirements extracted from various stakeholders of the buildings-energy domain. Overall, it aims to serve as a complete solution for stakeholders who want to optimise their business operations and gain valuable insights from their data. Its main offerings, provide enhanced accessibility to actual building-energy data, enabling users to enhance their data with valuable external sources. The platform ensures efficient and transparent data management, trusted data sharing/trading via an intuitive data marketplace allowing data monetisation. Additionally, users can benefit from insightful data analysis over their data, using the platform's pre- trained or user's custom-built analytics.

In this direction, the paper details the platform's different services bundles forming the different layers of its architecture, along with the foreseen interactions of the platform with the various software applications/tools for buildings, city authorities, and energy market stakeholders, also developed in the context of the BEYOND project.

It shall be noted that the BEYOND Big data platform is currently under validation in four large demonstration sites in Greece, Spain, Finland, and Serbia; encompassing various types of buildings (including offices, commercial and residential buildings), and including a wide range of users and data sources, diverse energy systems and assets. These demonstration activities are expected to

showcase the platform's offerings, attest to its value and serve as evidence supporting the overall vision of the BEYOND.

Acknowledgements

The work presented in this paper is carried out in the context of the BEYOND project - "A reference big data platform implementation and AI analytics toolkit toward innovative data sharing-driven energy service ecosystems for the building sector and beyond"; and has been co-funded by the European Unions' Horizon 2020 program under grant agreement No. 957020.

References

- [1] European Parliament and Council. Directive 2010/31/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 May 2010 on the energy performance of buildings. Official Journal of the European Union, L153:13–35, 2010.
- [2] BEYOND Consortium. On-line: <https://beyond-h2020.eu>, (Accessed: 05/09/2023)
- [3] European Commission. Energy Use in Buildings. Available online: <https://ec.europa.eu/energy/en/eu-buildings-factsheets-topics-tree/energy-use-buildings> (Accessed: 14/09/2023)
- [4] European Commission. Directive 2010/31/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 May 2010 on the energy performance of buildings (recast)
- [5] European Commission, COM (2016) 765, "Proposal for a directive amending Directive 2010/31/EU on the energy performance of buildings," 2016.
- [6] Energy efficiency directive Energy. Available at: https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficiency-targets-directive-and-rules/energy-efficiency-directive_en#:~:text=The%202023%20revised%20directive%20raises,the%202020%20reference%20scenario%20projections. (Accessed: 14 September 2023).
- [7] European Commission. Directive 2009/125/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 October 2009 Establishing a Framework for the Setting of Ecodesign Requirements for Energy-Related Products (Recast); European Commission: Brussels, Belgium, 2009.
- [8] European Commission. Regulation (EU) 2017/1369 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 July 2017 Setting a Framework for Energy Labelling and Repealing Directive 2010/30/EU; European Commission: Brussels, Belgium, 2017
- [9] A European green deal (no date) European Commission. Available at: https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en (Accessed: 15 September 2023). (Accessed: 14 September 2023).
- [10] Press corner European Commission - European Commission. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_20_1835 (Accessed: 14 September 2023).
- [11] Sepasgozar, S.M.; Davis, S. Construction technology adoption cube: An investigation on process, factors, barriers, drivers and decision makers using NVivo and AHP analysis. *Buildings* 2018, 8, 74. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings8060074>
- [12] Farzaneh, H.; Malehmirchegini, L.; Bejan, A.; Afolabi, T.; Mulumba, A.; Daka, P.P. Artificial Intelligence Evolution in Smart Buildings for Energy Efficiency. *Appl. Sci.* 2021, 11, 763. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11020763>
- [13] Ullah, Z.; Al-Turjman, F.; Mostarda, L.; Gagliardi, R. Applications of Artificial Intelligence and Machine learning in smart cities. *Comput. Commun.* 2020, 154, 313–323. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comcom.2020.02.069>

- [14] Zhao, Y.; Li, T.; Zhang, X.; Zhang, C. Artificial intelligence-based fault detection and diagnosis methods for building energy systems: Advantages, challenges, and the future. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 2019, 109, 85–101. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2019.04.021>
- [15] Mariano-Hernández, D.; Hernández-Callejo, L.; Zorita-Lamadrid, A.; Duque-Pérez, O.; García, F.S. A review of strategies for building energy management system: Model predictive control, demand side management, optimization, and fault detect & diagnosis. *J. Build. Eng.* 2021, 33, 101692. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.job.2020.101692>
- [16] Tabesh, P., Mousavidin, E. and Hasani, S., (2019). Implementing big data strategies: A managerial perspective. *Business Horizons*, 62(3), pp. 347-358.
- [17] Chen, P., Linc, C. and Wud, W., (2020). Big Data Management in healthcare: Adoption challenges and implications. *International Journal of Information Management*, 26(1), pp. 1-2.
- [18] Konanahalli, A.; Oyedele, L.; Marinelli, M.; Selim, G. *Big Data: A New Revolution in the UK Facilities Management Sector*; Royal Institution of Chartered Surveyors (RICS): London, UK, 2018.
- [19] Reyes-Veras, P.F.; Renukappa, S.; Suresh, S. Challenges faced by the adoption of big data in the Dominican Republic construction industry: An empirical study. *J. Inf. Technol. Constr.* 2021, 26, 812–831. DOI: 10.36680/j.itcon.2021.044
- [20] Yu, T.; Liang, X.; Wang, Y. Factors Affecting the Utilization of Big Data in Construction Projects. *J. Constr. Eng. Manag.* 2020, 146, 04020032. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)CO.1943-7862.0001807](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)CO.1943-7862.0001807)
- [21] Sun, S.; Cegielski, C.G.; Jia, L.; Hall, D.J. Understanding the Factors Affecting the Organizational Adoption of Big Data. *J. Comput. Inf. Syst.* 2018, 58, 193–203. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08874417.2016.1222891>
- [22] Bilal, M.; Oyedele, L.O.; Qadir, J.; Munir, K.; Ajayi, S.O.; Akinade, O.O.; Owolabi, H.A.; Alaka, H.A.; Pasha, M. Big Data in the construction industry: A review of present status, opportunities, and future trends. *Adv. Eng. Inform.* 2016, 30, 500–521. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aei.2016.07.001>
- [23] Atuahene, B.T.; Kanjanabootra, S.; Gajendran, T. Mapping the Barriers of Big Data Process in Construction: The Perspective of Construction Professionals. *Buildings* 2023, 13, 1963. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings13081963>
- [24] Silverio-Fernandez, M., Renukappa, S. and Suresh, S., Evaluating critical success factors for implementing smart devices in the construction industry: An empirical study in the Dominican Republic. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, 2019, 26(8), pp. 1625-1640.
- [25] Mahmoud Daneshmand et al., "Big Challenges for Big Data in the Smart Grid Era," *ECN Magazine*, 2017.
- [26] Chang, V., Xu, Y.K., Zhang, J. and Xu, Q., 2021. Research on intelligent manufacturing development approach for China's local valve industry. *Smart and Sustainable Built Environment*, 10(2), pp. 293-321. DOI:10.1108/SASBE-03-2021-0044
- [27] Sayah, Z., Kazar, O., Lejdel, B., Laouid, A. and Ghenabzia, A., 2021. An intelligent system for energy management in smart cities based on big data and ontology. *Smart and Sustainable Built Environment*, 10(2), pp. 169-192.
- [28] Bishnu P. Bhattarai et al., "Big Data Analytics in Smart Grids: State-of-the-Art, Challenges, Opportunities and Future Directions," *IET Research Journals*, pp. 1-15, 2019.
- [29] ETSI. (2020). SAREF Extension for Building. On-line: <https://saref.etsi.org/saref4bldg/v1.1.2/>, (Accessed: 05/09/2023)

- [30] ETSI. (2020). SAREF, On- line: <https://saref.etsi.org/saref4bldg/v1.1.2/>, (Accessed: 05/09/2023)
- [31] ETSI. (2020). Smart applications reference ontology, and extensions SAREF Portal. Available at: <https://saref.etsi.org/> (Accessed: 05/09/2023)
- [32] buildingSMART. Industry Foundation Classes (IFC). On-line: <https://technical.buildingsmart.org/standards/ifc>, (Accessed: 05/09/2023)
- [33] Hong, T. et al. (2015) ‘An ontology to represent energy-related occupant behavior in buildings. part II: Implementation of the DNAS framework using an XML schema’, Building and Environment, 94, pp. 196–205. doi:10.1016/j.buildenv.2015.08.006.
- [34] Creative Commons. On-line: <https://creativecommons.org/>, (Accessed: 05/09/2023)
- [35] The Linux Foundation. Community Data License Agreement. On-line: <https://cdla.dev/>, (Accessed: 05/09/2023)
- [36] Open Knowledge Foundation. Open Data Commons. On-line: <https://opendatacommons.org>, (Accessed: 05/09/2023)